

Shape optimisation with differentiated CAD-kernel for U-bend testcase

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A gradient-based optimisation of a parametric CAD model requires the calculation of shape sensitivities, i.e., the derivatives of surface points with respect to the design parameters. Typically, this information is not available within a CAD system and can be obtained by applying Automatic Differentiation (AD) to the CAD sources. This paper demonstrates the differentiated open-source CAD kernel OpenCascade Technology (OCCT) using the AD software tool ADOL-C (Automatic Differentiation by Overloading in C++) for the optimisation of pressure loss in a U-bend pipe. The U-bend geometry is parametrised in OCCT and its derivatives are used in CFD optimisation loops.

I. Introduction

To include CAD-models in the shape optimisation workflow one needs to find an effective way to compute CAD sensitivities. One of the strategies in industry is to build perturbed models and calculate shape derivatives with finite differences. This approach results in gradient inaccuracy and possible topology changes due to finite-step displacements.

While hand-differentiation of a complete CAD-system is unlikely to be feasible, the application of automatic differentiation (AD) tools proves to be a way forward. Xu et al.¹ apply AD in the NSPCC approach which uses the NURBS control points in the CAD-native boundary representation (BRep) as degrees of freedom. It works with the CAD-vendor neutral STEP file, although additional constraints need to be imposed to retain the desired continuity between NURBS patches.

Here we demonstrate the application of the AD-tool ADOL-C to the CAD system OCCT in order to enable parametric CAD optimisation. This overcomes the deficiencies of previous methods as there are no topological changes and constraints can be easily embedded directly in the CAD-model.

II. Automatic Differentiation of OpenCascade Technology

ADOL-C² is a software tool that uses the operator overloading concept to compute, in forward and reverse mode of automatic differentiation, first and higher derivatives of vector functions that are defined by computer programs written in C/C++. For the purpose of this paper, only one feature of ADOL-C is considered, i.e., the *traceless forward differentiation* - which computes first order derivatives in scalar and in vector mode.

The basis of automatic differentiation by overloading is the concept of **active** variables. All variables that may be considered as differentiable quantities at any part of the program must be of an **active** type - which is called **adouble** in ADOL-C. Therefore, the idea is to replace the declaration types of all relevant **real** variables by **adouble** type. To achieve this, several possible ways of ADOL-C integration into OCCT were considered, but only one was successful so far - the **typedef** approach. This approach is very intrusive because every **double**, even one not needed for differentiation, is replaced by **adouble**, but it is the fastest way of integration.

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III. Parametrisation

The U-bend under investigation, as shown in Figure 1, is a typical internal cooling channel. Its optimisation problem has already been studied³ where the design parameters are actually the control points of U-bend's B-spline surfaces. In this paper we propose a new parametrisation that is based on a cross-sectional design approach - the lofting. In particular, the part of the U-bend to be optimised is described by N -slices generated along a guiding pathline and approximated with a tool provided by OCCT. Each slice lies on a plane which is orthogonal to the pathline and consists of the 4 Bezier curves forming a closed wire and having in total 12 control points. The position of each control point on the plane is determined by a law of evolution of the control point along the pathline. The laws of evolution are described with B-spline curves. For this reason, the law's control points are the design parameters of the optimisation.

Figure 1: U-bend

IV. Results

The U-bend described above is subject to aerodynamic shape optimisation to reduce pressure losses between the inlet and outlet legs. For the CFD analysis an in-house solver *mgOpt* was used. It facilitates the geometric multi-grid method and implements the discrete adjoint method using AD. It was coupled with the differentiated OCCT to obtain gradient information driving the optimisation loop.

In Figure 2 the preliminary results of a simpler U-bend geometry optimisation are shown by means of flow velocity. The optimiser managed to suppress the separation bubble formed in the beginning of an outlet leg.

Figure 2: Velocity Magnitude

References

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